

Mesomorphic Characteristic and Phase Transitions of some Ester Mesogens : *p*-(*p*'-*n*-Alkoxy-cinnamoyloxy)propiofenones

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Twelve ester mesogens belonging to the homologous series *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxy-cinnamoyloxy)propiofenones have been synthesised. Enantiotropic nematic mesophase commences from the very first member and continues upto hexyl derivative. Polymesomorphism is shown from the butyl to hexyl derivatives. The latter members from heptyl derivative onwards exhibit enantiotropic smectic mesophase. Very large smectic mesophase range is obtained as compared to the nematic phase. The smectic phase shows focal-conic texture of the smectic A variety. The nematic phase is of threaded texture. The usual odd-even effect is observed.

THE present new ester mesogen series *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxy-cinnamoyloxy)propiofenones (1) is mesogenic with a wide mesomorphic range; the mesomorphic behaviour and its temperature dependence emphasise the significance of terminal *para*-substituents and central linkage.

Experimental

p-*n*-Alkoxybenzaldehydes were prepared by the alkylation of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde^{1,2}; *trans-p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamic acids from the corresponding *p*-*n*-alkoxybenzaldehydes and malonic acid³; *trans-p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyl chlorides from the corresponding *trans-p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamic acids³; and *p*-hydroxypropiofenone was prepared from phenylpropionate⁴.

Preparation of esters: A mixture of *p*-hydroxypropiofenone (0.01 mol) in dry pyridine (A.R.; 10 ml) and *p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyl chloride (0.015 mol) in dry pyridine was warmed for 1 h and allowed to stand overnight. It was then acidified with dilute HCl and the resulting solid was washed with very dilute NaOH solution followed by water. Dodecyl to octadecyl members of the series were purified by alumina column chromatography using benzene-petroleum ether (60 : 40) as eluent. The crude solid was crystallised from ethanol or benzene-petroleum ether (80 : 20) as fine needles (Table 1). The elemental analyses conform with the calculated values.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE PROPIOFENONES

Sl. no.	R	Transition temp. (°C)		
		Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
1.	Methyl	—	141.0	167.0
2.	Ethyl	(111.0) ^a	134.5	174.0
3.	Propyl	(129.0) ^a	136.5	166.0
4.	Butyl	122.5	142.0	168.0
5.	Pentyl	106.0	151.0	163.0
6.	Hexyl	104.0	157.5	163.5
7.	Heptyl	097.5	—	161.5
8.	Octyl	093.5	—	162.0
9.	Decyl	095.0	—	160.0
10.	Dodecyl	098.0	—	157.5
11.	Hexadecyl	102.5	—	148.0
12.	Octadecyl	102.0	—	152.0

^aValues obtained by extrapolation.

The transitions were studied by the usual optical method as well as by using Kofler heating stage polarising microscope.

Results and Discussion

Enantiotropic nematic mesophase is exhibited from the very first member and continues upto hexyl derivative. The transitions are plotted against the number of carbon atoms of the alkyl chain (Fig. 1). The solid-mesomorphic transition curve drops very steeply except at the third derivative where a little rise is observed upto the eighth derivative. Again it rises somewhat upto the hexadecyl member and then levels off.

From the fourth homologue polymesomorphism is exhibited upto the sixth member and thereafter only smectic mesophase is exhibited. The usual odd-even effect in the case of nematic transitions is observed. The nematic-isotropic transition curves show a falling trend as the alkyl chain-length increases.

Fig. 1. Plots of number of carbon atoms vs temperature of the propiophenones : (●) solid-mesomorphic, (○) nematic-isotropic, (Δ) smectic-nematic, (⊗) smectic-isotropic.

The π -electron density of the central group coupled with the increased chain-length as the series is ascended, gives rise to a polarity-polarisability ratio which favours initially the formation of only nematic phase followed by polymesomorphism upto the hexyl derivative and then smectic mesophase till the last homologue. After the hexyl homologue, the lateral adhesions and forces due to greater polarisability are predominant over the terminal attractions resulting into exhibition of smectic mesophase only.

The smectic-nematic transition shows a very steep rising tendency as the series is ascended upto the seventh member. The smectic-nematic and smectic-isotropic transition curves show a rising tendency upto a certain maximum followed by a smooth fall and then levelling off as the series is ascended. With a greater steep falling tendency of the solid-mesomorphic curve, the mesomorphic range is much widened.

The nematic phase is of threaded texture and the smectic phase of focal conic texture of smectic A variety as observed by optical as well as contact methods.

The present homologous series is compared for their molecular characteristics and thermal stabilities with other homologous series⁶: (G) *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)acetophenones, (A) *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)propiophenones, (K) *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)acetophenone, (M) ethyl *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinna-

moyloxy)benzoates and (V) biphenyl 4-*trans-p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamates (Table 2).

Series	Present series	G	A	K	M	V
Nematic-Isotropic (C ₅ -C ₆)	163.0	134.7	120.0	087.0	119.7	206.0 (C ₁ -C ₄)
Smectic-Nematic or Smectic-Isotropic (C ₁₅ -C ₁₈)	152.5	139.6	123.5	100.1	117.0	156.0
Commencement of smectic mesophase	C ₄	C ₂	C ₄	C ₂	C ₂	C ₁

The average smectic-nematic or smectic-isotropic and nematic-isotropic thermal stabilities for the present series are higher than those for the series A; the longer vinylcarboxy group with an added double bond increasing π -electron density⁶ in the case of the present series will enhance the overall polarisability of molecules causing higher thermal stabilities. A similar trend is observed in the case of series G and K; both smectic and nematic thermal stabilities of series G are higher than those for series K for the same reasons. Again the smectic-nematic or smectic-isotropic and nematic-isotropic thermal stabilities in the case of the present series are higher than those for series M. Very strong terminal attractions in the case of the present series developed due to terminal polar propionyl -COC₂H₅ group as compared to the terminal -COOC₂H₅ in case of series M, enhance the overall polarisability of the molecules of the present series, consequently, thermal stabilities are increased, though as such ester linkage is known to depress thermal stabilities⁷.

However, the biphenyl unit in case of series V obviously contributes to the lateral attractions in a larger measure as compared to the propionyl group of the present series; this makes the average thermal stabilities for series V to assume a little higher values than those for the present series. While commencement of smectic mesophase is comparable as far as the present series and series A are concerned, the somewhat early commencement of smectic mesophase in the case of series M can be seen as due to relatively greater predominance of lateral attractions, and its considerably late beginning in the case of series V homologues as a result of greater aromaticity on account of the biphenyl unit at the other terminal.

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